

Have You Been Exposed to Aircraft Engine Oil? Candidate Biomarkers of Exposure

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ABBREVIATIONS

AChE	Acetylcholinesterase
BChE	Butyrylcholinesterase
TAPs	Triaryl phosphates
TCP	Tri-cresyl phosphate

ABSTRACT

Most aircraft flying today use bleed air to provide air conditioning to the aircraft. The problem with this design is that low levels of oil leak through the engine oil seals into the aircraft air in normal engine operation and when engine seals wear/fail, higher levels of oil mist enters the aircraft. Since the aircraft engine oil contains several percent of neurotoxic triaryl phosphates (TAPs) as anti-wear agent/fire retardant. Exposure to aircraft engine oil causes serious health problems to aircrew and passengers. This situation presents the following problems: 1) how is exposure documented, 2) are safer TAPs available or designable 3) why are some individuals more resistant to the effects of TAP exposure than others? 4) is treatment possible for TAP exposure?

INTRODUCTION

The toxicity of tri-cresyl phosphate (TCP) esters has been known as early as 1899.¹ Mixed TCP isomers, primarily of the meta- and para- isomers are used in aircraft engines as anti-wear additives in aviation engine oils.² Most commercial and military aircraft are designed to ventilate and pressurize the cabin and flight deck with air that is extracted (or “bled”) from the compressors in each engine. This design using pressurized air to keep the oil in the engine oil bearing sumps enables low levels of oil to leak through the engine oil seals into the aircraft air in normal engine operation and when engine seals wear/fail higher levels of oil mist enters the aircraft.^{3,4} This “bleed air” is not filtered, so when oil from the engine contaminates the ventilation fraction of the air, the aircrew and passengers are supplied with air contaminated with engine oil that contains 2.2-5.6% TCP mixed esters.² Debate between the airline industry and aircrew and passengers who have suffered neurological damage prompted this study that is aimed at documenting exposures to these mixed meta- and para- TCP isomers in aviation engine oil fumes. The methods employed in these studies make use of a rapid isolation of target biomarker proteins whose active site serine residues are susceptible to adduction by either the triaryl phosphates directly or by metabolites generated from the TAPs through a process termed bioactivation carried out by specific cytochromes P450. Antibodies specific for a given biomarker protein are covalently attached to paramagnetic beads (~2 μ diameter) allowing isolation of the target biomarker protein to a high degree of purity in a single step. The purified target proteins are cut into smaller peptides by specific proteases (usually trypsin) and analyzed by mass spectrometry (MS) which will not only quantify the modification on the active site serine but will also reveal the added mass of the adduct on the active site peptide fragment.⁵ Protocols have been developed for the rapid purification of several potential biomarker proteins for analyzing the extent of exposure to triaryl phosphates using MS to analyze the TAP modification of the active site serine residues of the

specific biomarker proteins. Earlier studies are reviewed that illustrate the potential toxicity of TAP exposures. Approaches for identifying potentially safer TAP anti-wear additives are discussed as well as a means of mitigating the conversion of TAPs to highly toxic metabolites. It is clear that exposure to aircraft engine oil and perhaps hydraulic fluid fumes represent a significant health hazard to both aircrew and passengers, and that exposure can also compromise flight safety when crews are impaired inflight. For existing aircraft, retrofitting the bleed air system with suitable filters may decrease the exposures of cabin occupants to hazardous chemicals. A better solution is that used in the Boeing 787, where bleed air is not used to provide air conditioning to the aircraft cabin. Clinical laboratory protocols need to be completed that will provide an accurate measure of an individual's exposure to the types of TCPs in oil fumes. Because there are other sources of TCP exposure in the environment (e.g., electronics, flame retardants), it will be important to collect baseline TCP exposure data from individuals who have not flown during a fume event for comparison purposes. Inter-individual differences in metabolism of toxic TAP molecules most likely explain the differential susceptibility to exposures. These individual differences need to be further explored. For example, the enzyme carboxylesterase varies widely among individuals and serves as an effective "sponge" for capturing toxic TAPs and their metabolites, such that a person with low levels of carboxylesterase may be more susceptible to toxic effects of TAP exposure, based on experiments reported by Grubič *et al.*⁶

METHODS

In response to queries from an airline pilot union starting in 2004, our research team committed to developing methods to document exposure to tricresyl phosphates onboard aircraft during an oil fume event. This paper describes the approaches to identify blood biomarkers of exposure to the blends of TCPs added to aviation engine oils ("D125"). Of note, the majority of TCP toxicity research-to-date has focused on either the single ToCP isomer or the combination of "ortho" isomers of TCP. However, because the total ortho isomer content of TCPs

in engine oils is expected to be less than 0.2%, we have purposefully focused our biomarker development work on the commercial meta/para TCP isomer blends, having obtained samples of the two blends added to these aviation oils.

RESULTS

A survey of smoke/fume incident databases maintained by the US Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) indicated that US airlines reported an average of 0.2 fume events per 1000 flights during the six-year period of January 1, 2007 to December 31, 2012.⁷ The reported fume events were specific for either oil or hydraulic fluid fumes in the bleed air. Based on the reported number of flights operated by US airlines during that period, the reported frequency calculates to 11,728 incidents during the 6-year period or 1,955 fume incidents per year, i.e. 5.4 incidents/day. Notably, US airlines are not required to report ground-based fume events or those events after which a mechanical fault was not identified. As such, the 5.4 incidents/day estimate only represents a sub-set of actual fume events. Still, this dataset illustrates that fume events are a daily occurrence on the US fleet. Further, under reporting has been widely recognized and the design of the oil system allows low level oil leakage in normal operations.^{3,4}

Do these fume events represent a public health problem as well as a significant safety issue?

The potential for flight safety to be compromised when airline pilots breathe oil fumes inflight has long been recognized.⁸ Airline flight safety regulators in Europe and Australia have attributed documented incidents of pilot impairment and incapacitation to inflight exposure to engine oil fumes.^{9,10} Other cases attribute increased pilot workload to the presence of oil fumes inflight.¹¹ In less-publicized oil fume events, crew unions in Europe, Australia, the US and Canada have received reports from pilots who describe significant impairment during essential phases of flight (usually descent and landing) during/after breathing oil fumes onboard. In some cases, pilots report symptoms consistent with exposure to asphyxiant compounds such as carbon monoxide

Figure 1 — US Airways Boeing 767-200, registration N251AY performing flight US-1041 from Saint Thomas (US Virgin Islands) to Charlotte, NC (USA) with 174 passengers. In March 2010 US Airways confirmed, that engine oil had leaked through a faulty seal into the bleed air supplying the air condition system. Both flight crew received permanent injuries.

and hexane. Figure 1 and published description of the fume event that appeared in *The Aviation Herald* (<http://avherald.com/h?article=425f6a41&opt=0>) indicate that fume events represent not only a public health issue, but a serious inflight safety issue.

In an earlier publication,¹² an epidemiological study based on flights where fume events have caused documented health effects to cabin crew was suggested. The suggestion appears below.

“The data presented in both the report for DfT by the Institute of Environment and Health (Cranfield Ref No YE29016V) and the ITCOBA Conference of 11 October 2011 quite clearly point to the need for more relevant studies on the effects of TAP exposure on aircraft occupants. The studies should include not only fume event-exposed aircrew, but also passengers who greatly outnumber exposed aircrew and include some of the more vulnerable members of society—the old, young, and unborn. There really is no need to set up more data gathering investigations as there have already been a large number of individuals exposed to significant fume events as shown in the literature and other reports documented by passengers and crew, which are in the public domain.^{13,14} Passenger manifests for flights

with documented and significant fume events involving engine oil would be a rich source for epidemiological studies. Reliable conclusions cannot be drawn from monitoring a small number of flights where no fume events occurred. The incident noted above, where two pilots lost their medical certificates and most of the crew have been unable to return to work many months later, provides an excellent example where the current health status of the passengers on the same flight would be highly informative, as would epidemiological studies on other similar flights where fume events have resulted in ill health of the air crew. Aviation regulators should promulgate and enforce passenger right-to-know regulations to enable passengers who have been exposed to engine oil fumes to seek appropriate medical care.”

Potential biomarkers from human blood for exposure to triaryl phosphates

Several proteins in human blood have been examined as potential biomarkers of TAP exposure. Plasma butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) has been used for many years as an indication of OP exposures, especially in the agricultural industry for a measure of OP insecticide exposure. Initial experiments carried out in our own laboratory and in collaboration with Dr. Oksana Lockridge from the University of Nebraska showed that while BChE was readily inhibited by the active metabolite of ToCP cresylbenzodioxaphosphorin oxide (CBDP), over a short period of time, the cresyl group was lost through an “aging” reaction, leaving only a phosphoserine at the active site of BChE. The same phenomenon was observed in blood samples from individuals who had flown recently.¹⁵ Following this observation, we looked for a blood protein that did not lose the cresyl group through the aging process after exposure to the D125 blend of commercial TCPs that is added to aviation engine oils. Other potential blood proteins that might serve as biomarkers for TAP exposure include acylpeptide hydrolase (APH) which is a useful biomarker for OP insecticide exposure, carboxylesterase which is highly sensitive to OP inhibition, however in blood, it is present in monocytes which have short half-lives of 1-7 days and neuropathy target esterase (NTE), the inhibition of which

is thought to be responsible for the paralysis observed following the consumption of ToCP contaminated ginger extracts during prohibition in the United States.¹⁶ We cloned the catalytic domain of NTE, expressed it in *E. coli* and found it to be quite unstable, making it more difficult to develop as a potential biomarker of TAP exposure. Further, paralysis does not appear to be a common symptom of exposures to TAPs used in the aircraft industry.

Evaluation of AChE as a potential biomarker for TCP exposures

Of the potential biomarkers of exposure available in human blood, AChE has two advantages: 1) it doesn't age with the loss of the cresyl group like BChE,¹⁷ and 2) it has a much longer half-life in blood, 33 d vs. 11 d for BChE. AChE does have a disadvantage of being less sensitive to inhibition by some OP compounds than BChE. Incubation of AChE with the active metabolite of ToCP, resulted in 170 mass units added to the peptide containing the active site serine of the AChE. Interestingly, while the inhibition of BChE requires bioactivation of the TAP, AChE can be inhibited by the un-bioactivated TAP.¹⁸

In vitro analysis of BChE by bioactivated TAPs

Inhibition of BChE activity by various triaryl phosphates was used to identify potentially safer TAP anti-wear agents for aircraft engine oil. The results suggested that tri-*p*-cresyl phosphate and tri-*tert*-butyl phenyl phosphate did not generate inhibitors of BChE when bioactivated by an *in vitro* microsomal bioactivation system. These experiments were followed up by *in vivo* testing of tri-*p*-cresyl phosphate and the tri-*tert*-butyl-phenyl phosphate para isomer.

In vivo analysis of TAP inhibition of specific enzymes

In vivo analysis of enzyme inhibition by feeding different TAPs to mice as a follow-on study to *in vitro* experiments aimed at identifying safer anti-wear additives for aircraft engine oils showed that tri-(*p*-*tert*-butylphenyl) phosphate generated the lowest level of inhibition of the three potential biomarker enzymes tested *in vivo* (plasma cholinesterase (BChE), acylpeptide hydrolase

and carboxylesterase. On the other hand D125 was a potent inhibitor of BChE, liver APH and plasma carboxylesterase. TpCP strongly inhibited plasma carboxylesterase and liver APH. Examination of the data from *in vitro* and *in vitro* inhibition indicates that it is important to follow up *in vitro* screening with *in vivo* analyses.

Why some individuals are more sensitive to TAP exposures than others

This is as yet an unsolved question. It is well-known that levels of specific cytochrome P450s vary from one individual to another and that mutations exist in cytochrome P450s that may increase or decrease activity against a given substrate. A fundamental question is whether higher rates of bioactivation (hydroxylation) of TAPs is beneficial or harmful to an individual--this question needs to be examined. It is clear that bioactivation of TAPs greatly increases the inhibition of plasma cholinesterase.¹⁹ However, it needs to be determined if the overall physiological effect of variation of level of given P450s on the toxicity associated with a given exposure is greater or less with rates of bioactivation. Variability in levels of other enzyme levels is also a relatively unstudied question. For example, carboxylesterase which readily interacts with TAPs varies in the human population by at least 18-fold.²⁰ Studies with rodents have shown that carboxylesterase levels are important in determining the toxicity of exposure to organophosphorus nerve agents, compounds with the similar enzyme inhibition properties to TAPs.⁶

Is it possible to mitigate an OP exposure?

As noted above, some enzymes are only inactivated by TAP metabolites generated by one or more cytochrome P-450s (bioactivation). Blocking the bioactivation step may serve to reduce the consequences of exposure. Naringenin, a natural component of grapefruit, inhibits the bioactivation of D125 to an inhibitor of plasma cholinesterase at physiologically relevant concentrations.¹⁹ This approach provides a simple screening step for approaches that may mitigate the consequences of TAP exposures. It also fact suggests that naringenin ingested subsequent to a fume event may

offer some protective effect by slowing or blocking the conversion of TAPs into more toxic metabolites. This can be tested experimentally.

Importance of blood sample analysis by certified clinical laboratories

The Clinical Laboratory Improvement Amendments (CLIA) regulate laboratory testing and require clinical laboratories to be certificated by their state as well as the Center for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) before they can accept human samples for diagnostic testing. Thus, as we develop protocols for analyzing blood samples for analysis, it will be important to correlate with CLIA-certified laboratories for blood sample analysis. Ideally, there will be a number of laboratories worldwide that make use of standardized assays to analyze samples.

CONCLUSIONS

It is clear that fume events are an ongoing problem.² The approaches described here are aimed at 1) documenting TAP exposures, 2) understanding the physiological consequences of exposures, 3) understanding the genetic variability of susceptibility to TAP exposures, 3) addressing the possibility of safer TAP anti-wear additives, 4) examining possible treatments for mitigating exposures and 5) developing collaborations with certified clinical laboratories to analyze blood samples of exposed individuals to document TAP exposure.

Recommendations

A systematic survey of the neurological, respiratory, and other symptoms reported by crewmembers during and after documented exposure to engine oil fumes should be mandated by the appropriate regulators. In addition, regulators should ensure that passengers onboard incident flights are notified, provided with information to share with their doctors, and asked to report health effects so that the regulators (or some neutral third party) can collect and analyze incident-specific data in order to better define the health impacts of exposure. It is not too late to carry out such epidemiological studies.

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